

Control of spiral nematode on rice

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Six nematicides against spiral nematode *Helicotylenchus abunaamai* were evaluated. Clay pots filled with sterilized soil (500 g/pot) were infested with 1,000 nematodes each. One week later, the granular nematicides aldicarb, phorate, fensulfothion, carbofuran, and diazinon at 2 and 4 kg ai/ha and the fumigant dibromochloropropane (DBCP) at 6 and 12 liters/ha were applied. Each treatment was replicated four times. Annapurna seedlings were transplanted after 15 d at 1 plant/ pot. Nematode populations and plant growth were evaluated 90 d after transplanting.

DBCP at 12 liters/ha was most effective in reducing nematode

Effect of 6 nematicides on spiral nematode populations and plant growth. Bhubaneswar, India.

Nematicide	Dosage (ai/ha)	Nematode recovery/500 g soil ^a	Plant mean dry wt (g)
Aldicarb	2 kg	1878	15.6
	4 kg	1330	16.4
Phorate	2 kg	875	16.4
	4 kg	556	16.4
Fensulfothion	2 kg	1993	1.53
	4 kg	1456	15.7
Carbofuran	2 kg	1205	16.6
	4 kg	819	16.8
Diazinon	2 kg	2141	15.2
	4 kg	1699	15.4
DBCP	6 liters	871	16.6
	12 liters	280	17.2
Control		3854	15.2
CD (0.01)			0.4

^aMean of 4 replications, Initial population = 1000/500 g soil.

populations, followed by phorate at 4 kg ai/ha (see table). Carbofuran (4 kg ai/ ha), DBCP (6 liters/ ha), and phorate (2 kg ai/ha) brought nematode populations below the inoculum level.

Dry plant weight was highest with 12 liters DBCP/ha. It was also significantly higher than that of the control with carbofuran and phorate (both rates), DBCP (6 liters/ ha), and aldicarb (4 kg ai/ha). □

Soil and Crop Management

Insecticide-zinc interactions in lowland rice

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We studied the effects on yield of soil-applied granular insecticides, Zn, and their interactions during the southwest monsoon season Jul-Oct 1982. The experiment was laid out in a factorial combination of 3 levels of insecticides (no insecticide, carbofuran at 0.75 kg ai/ha, phorate at 1.0 kg ai/ ha) and 2 levels of Zn (no ZnSO₄ and 25 kg ZnSO₄/ha).

Carbofuran (2,3-Dihydro- 2,2-dimethyl-7-benzofuranyl-methyl-carbamate), available in 3% granules commercially, is a broad-spectrum insecticide recommended at 0.5 to 0.75 kg ai/ha for rice. Phorate (0.0-Diethyl

S [(ethylthio) methyl] phosphorodithioate), available in 10% granules commercially, is recommended at 1 kg ai/ ha. The experiment in wetland rice at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India (11°N, 77°E, and 427 m above mean sea level) used standard management practices. The soil contained 1.1% organic C, 196-9.5-200 ppm available NPK, 598 ppm total soil N, and 0.4 ppm DTPA extractable Zn.

Test variety was IR20.

Application of either insecticide or Zn increased yields significantly (see table). However, the increases depended on the level of the other factor. The effect of Zn was highest when phorate was applied, 20% increase against 10% for carbofuran and 15% without insecticide. The effect of insecticide was also slightly higher when Zn was applied. □

Effects of insecticide and Zn application on IR20 yield. Coimbatore, India, Jul-Oct 1982.

Insecticide	Yield (t/ha)		Difference	
	No Zn	25 kg ZnSO ₄ /ha	t/ha	%
No insecticide	2.81	3.23	0.42	15
Carbofuran 3% G 0.75	3.45	3.78	0.33	10
Phorate 10% G 1.0	3.37	4.06	0.69	20
AV	3.21	3.69	0.48	15
CD .01 = 0.20 t/ha				